

INFUSION AND POLYMERIZATION OF THICK GLASS/ELIUM® ACRYLIC THERMOPLASTIC RESIN COMPOSITES

ZEBRA PROJECT
Zero wastE Blade ReseArch

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ZEBRA: Zero waste Blade ReseArch project

► Circular economy

The life cycle of a wind turbine

The global rate of Wind turbine installations

Examples of blade repurposing

Source: Accelerating wind turbine blade circularity, Wind Europe

Source: Sustainable decommissioning: wind turbine blade recycling

ZEBRA project: Zero waste Blade ReseArch

Project objectives

Accelerate the industry transition to a circular economy by designing and manufacturing the first 100% recyclable wind blades, using the thermoplastic resin ELIUM[®], developed by Arkema.

The 62m blade manufactured by LM Wind Power using Arkema's Elium[®] resin, Ponferrada, Spain, March 2022.

ZEBRA project: IRT Jules Verne activities

Manufacturing

Process Health Monitoring

Modeling and Simulation

Mechanical testing and simulation

Automation development

Structural Health Monitoring

Repair of blade structures

Recycling/techno-co-eco analysis

Modeling and simulation of the infusion process

► Context

Study objectives

- Establish physics-based simulations
 - Evaluate the model accuracy with experiments
 - Predict the process behavior for thick and complex parts

Liquid resin infusion process (LRI)

Material characterization

- Parameter/model identification and modeling

Experimental validation

- Validation of simulation results and assumptions
- Infusion simulations of growing complexity

Decision support

- Prediction for new parts

Modeling and simulation of the infusion process

Simulation strategy: parts with growing complexity

Thin parts
2D/3D

Technological part
2D/3D

Thick parts
3D

Ply drop-off
3D

Wind blade root
2D/3D

Heat transfer
Resin polymerization
Permeability measurement
Infusion strategy
Effect of gravity

Thickness variation
Effect of the distribution medium
Transverse flow
Effect of ply drop-off
Geometrical non-linearities

Modeling and simulation of the infusion process

► Simulation strategy

- Permeability of preform and flow medium
- Compression behaviour
- Resin viscosity and surface properties
- DSC tests, polymerization model and parameter identification

- Simplifications
- Assumptions

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- Simulation tool: PAM-RTM®
- Flow and polymerization

- Repeatability experiments
- Data acquisition

- Comparison between simulation and experiments

Infusion tests and process health monitoring

► Process Health Monitoring

► Infusion test bench

- Evaluate sensors dedicated to control infusion process
- Part/mold/vacuum bag embedded sensors/control without contact

OPC UA communication protocol

Vis/IR cameras

Thermocouple

Pressure sensors

Heat Flux

Dielectric sensors

Process Health Monitoring

Modeling and process simulation

► Process physics

Experiment	Infusion A	Infusion B
Part thickness (mm)	25	25
Initial viscosity (Pa.s)	0.094	0.122
Initial temperature (°C)	24.8	19.6

► Flow in porous media

Continuity equation $div(\vec{V}) = 0$

Darcy's law $\vec{V} = \frac{-K}{\mu} \nabla P$

► Heat transfer

$$\rho c_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \rho_r c_{p,r} \vec{V} \cdot \nabla T = -\nabla \cdot (\lambda \nabla T) + \dot{R}$$

► Polymerization kinetics

$$\dot{R} = \rho_r \Delta H \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} \quad \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} = f(t, \alpha)$$

\dot{R} : source term related to polymerization

Material characterization

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) tests

DSC scans

Thermal Analysis DSC Q200

- Isothermal and dynamic DSC scans
- Elium® 190 XO/SA mixture

Identification

Semi-empirical Arrhenius-type autocatalytic model

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = A_1 \exp\left(\frac{-E_1}{RT}\right) (1 - \alpha)^{n_1} + A_2 \exp\left(\frac{-E_2}{RT}\right) \alpha^{n_2} (\alpha_{max} - \alpha)^{n_3} \quad [2]$$

[1] Y. Denis et al., ESAFORM, Kraków, Poland, 2023

[2] N. Han et al., "Experimental and computational analysis of the polymerization overheating in thick glass/Elium® acrylic thermoplastic resin composites," *Compos B Eng*, vol. 202, p. 108430, 2020.

Modeling and process simulation

► Polymerization kinetics model

Validation and implementation

Comparison with experiments

- Sensitivity analysis
- Validation of the curing model with FreeFem

Implementation into PAM-RTM

- Experimental DSC curves fitting to a semi-empirical Arrhenius-type autocatalytic model
- Model parameters identified and used as input to PAM-RTM© simulations
- Implementation on Python, FreeFem and

ESI© Pam-RTM

Fig. 2. A schematic view of the water bath experiment together with the dimensions and the thermocouple location.

Modeling and process simulation

► Validation with experiments: flow front position

Filling factor

- Good agreement between flow simulations and experiments in the in-plane directions
- Perspective: validation with infusion tests and flow prediction through the part thickness

Modeling and process simulation

► Validation with experiments: resin polymerization

- Comparison between A and B experiments and simulation
- Virtual sensors placed at the part surface 1, 2 and 3 at the same positions
- Deviations at the part surface/good agreement through the thickness

Experiment Number	Infusion A	Infusion B
Initial temperature (°C)	24.8	19.6
Peak temperature (°C)	≈65	≈60
Time to peak	2h58min	3h52min

Modeling and simulation

► Predictions for a 40 mm thick part

Filling time (s)

Température (°C)

Polymerization degree

Thick lay-up with ply drop-off

► Material assignment

Objective: thicker part (65.5 mm) with new geometrical complexity

Regions of different stacking

Part infusion

65 mm

3D extrusion

Layer_15_650	1314.15	UD 1302_K_sst	Makro Fiber
Layer_16_638	1416.16	UD 1302_K_sst	Makro Fiber
Layer_17_620	1516.17	UD 1302_K_sst	Makro Fiber
Layer_18_610	1617.18	UD 1302_K_sst	Makro Fiber
Layer_19_610	1718.19	Bias006_K_sst	Makro Fiber
Layer_20_600	1819.20	Bias006_K_sst	Makro Fiber
Layer_21_600	1920.21	Bias006_K_sst	Makro Fiber
Layer_22_590	2021.22	Bias006_K_sst	Makro Fiber
Layer_23_590	2122.23	UD 1302_K_sst	Makro Fiber
Layer_24_580	2223.24	UD 1302_K_sst	Makro Fiber
Layer_25_570	2324.25	Bias006_K_sst	Makro Fiber
Layer_26_570	2425.26	Bias006_K_sst	Makro Fiber
Layer_27_570	2526.27	Bias006_K_sst	Makro Fiber
Layer_28_560	2627.28	Bias006_K_sst	Makro Fiber
Layer_29_560	2728.29	UD 1302_K_sst	Makro Fiber
Layer_30_560	2829.30	UD 1302_K_sst	Makro Fiber
Layer_31_540	2931.31	Bias006_K_sst	Makro Fiber
Layer_32_540	3031.32	Bias006_K_sst	Makro Fiber
Layer_33_540	3132.33	Bias006_K_sst	Makro Fiber

- Automatization of material assignment

Predictions for thick parts

► Polymerization behaviour in drop-off parts

- Illustration of a portion of a wind blade root
- Evolution of thickness from 65 mm (101 plies) to 2 mm (4 plies)
- Three sensors located at the part surface at 65 mm (1), 40 mm (2) and 2 mm (3)

Accomplished work and perspectives

Simple parts

Experimental validation, permeability measurement, process monitoring, sensor testing and model adjustment.

Thick parts

Correlation of the in-plane flow with experiments for thick parts. Polymerization kinetics and exothermic reaction.

Mold simulation

Modeling the flow and polymerization considering the mold, assigning the mold materials and parameters and studying the influence on the resin kinetics.

Technological part

Modeling the infusion process, correlation with experimental acquisitions, influence of gravity and optimization of the infusion scenario.

Thick parts with drop-off

Flow and polymerization simulations for thick parts and zones of ply drop-off. Comparison with experiments, implementation of defects (race-tracking), prediction and process optimization.

Wind blade root

Simulation of a complex part by implementing the hypotheses taken from previously studied cases.

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DE VOS USINES

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